

IMPROVEMENT OF CONTINUOUS PROFESSIONAL METHODOLOGY OF HISTORY TEACHERS BASED ON AN INTEGRATED APPROACH

Abduraimov Ikromjon Ravshanbekovich

Head of the Department of "Pedagogy and Psychology, Educational Technologies" of the National Center for Training Pedagogues in New Methods of Syrdarya Region, independent researcher

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Abstract. *This article aims to increase on the requirements for the level of general knowledge and professional development methodology improvement of history teachers on the basis of a continuous professional development course, the goal of tomorrow's perspective is the formation of creative, qualified specialists who can meet the requirements., History teachers teach history on an integrated basis, abandoning the oral teaching method. teaching, teaching multimedia applications based ondigital technologies and independent work.*

Key words: *competence development, professional development, integrative, multimedia, interactive methods, modeling, competence.*

INTRODUCTION: Today, in the educational system of developed countries in the world, the Integrative approach in pedagogical researches related to improving the quality of education, ensuring inter-disciplinarity of educational subjects - taking into account, relying on, combining and balancing the knowledge, skills, qualifications and experiences from various disciplines. implies development. "Integration" as an educational goal is to provide the student with knowledge that reflects the connection of separate parts of the world as a system, from the first stages of learning the child is aimed at imagining the world as a single entity in which all elements are interconnected.

In the educational process, teachers do not see the intersubjectivity of history in the teaching methodology, without which it is impossible to understand and fully study the essence of many phenomena of nature and society. The very concept of "integration" is widely used in the development of modern society. Integration processes can occur within already established systems - in this case, they lead to an increase in its integrity and organizational level, as well as the emergence of a new system from previously unrelated elements. The socio-economic reforms implemented in the educational system are one of the urgent issues of training highly qualified personnel, in particular, developing the competence of history teachers based on an integrated approach, improving their methods.

Perspectives of socio-political development are of theoretical and methodological significance for understanding the essence of many phenomena of nature and society, the socialization and culturalization of young people determine the future of the country, the preservation and development of national cultural traditions, values, and the professional development of teachers in continuous professional development. An integrative approach to research is becoming an urgent task.

As one of the main strategies of our republic, important results are being achieved in social and humanitarian sciences - history, philosophy, jurisprudence, archeology, oriental studies,

cultural heritage of the peoples of Uzbekistan, linguistics and literary studies, art studies and other fields¹. One of the most important encyclopedias in the world in its field, the only one in Central Asia and the first created in Uzbekistan "Encyclopedia of World Philosophy" was prepared and published in 2020, as a product of a new era, is a clear example of this.

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-6108 of November 6, 2020² and Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 25, 2021 No. PQ-4963 on measures to support research activities in the field of public education and to introduce a continuous professional development system³ accepted.

In accordance with the decision, it was decided to improve the system of retraining and upgrading the qualifications of leaders, specialists and pedagogues working in the field of public education, and to create the scientific foundations of general secondary education.

Resolution No. 25 of January 17, 2022 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Approving the regulation on the procedure for the organization of the system of continuous professional development of public education workers" was adopted. Based on the decision, a mechanism was developed to increase the level of competence and improve the professional skills of the staff of public education through the special electronic platform "Continuous Vocational Education", which covers the process of growth of the personal professional potential of public education employees in accordance with the needs of the individual and society.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS: The methodology of teaching subjects based on the national curriculum at all stages of the continuing education system requires great skill from pedagogues, which in turn increases the level of creativity and competence of teachers in the development of creative-research, practical activity experience in professional development courses.

encourages development. In continuous professional development, there is a reason to conduct research on the improvement of the mechanisms of application of interactive educational technologies and strategies to the educational process.

Studies on various aspects of the relevance of the problem of integration of subjects as a basis for the development of an integrated approach to educational content Jan Amos Comenius Grammar and philosophy, philosophy and literature interdependence V.F. Odoyevsky, K.D. Ushinsky V.V. Davydov, A.V. Zaporozhets, Yu.A. Samarin, D.B. Elkonin, B.P. Yusov, D.B. Kabalevsky, E.B. Abdullin, E.V. Nikolaeva, N.A. Menchinskaya, B.M. Kedrov M.S. Pak's O.M. Sichivitsa, N.T. Conducted by Kostyuk et al.

Social and economic reforms implemented in the educational process, training of highly qualified personnel, in particular, psychological aspects of the development of the competence of teachers in the methodology of teaching history based on an integrated approach L.S. Rubinshtein, A. Maslow, A. Leontev, M. G. Davletshin, E. Goziev, V.M. Karimova, R.I. Sunnatova, N.S. Safaev, Z.T. Nishonova⁴.

¹“Ўзбекистоннинг янги тараққиёт даврида таълим-тарбия ва илм-фан соҳаларини ривожлантириш чора-тадбирлар тўғрисида”ги Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг 2020-йил 6-ноябрдаги ПФ-6108-сон Фармони

²“Ўзбекистоннинг янги тараққиёт даврида таълим-тарбия ва илм-фан соҳаларини ривожлантириш чора-тадбирлар тўғрисида”ги Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг 2020-йил 6-ноябрдаги ПФ-6108-сон Фармони

³Вазирлар Маҳкамасининг 2022 йил 17 январдаги 25-сон қарори

⁴(Рубинштейн С.Л. Основы общей психологии. – СПб.: Питер, 2013. – 713 с.; Маслоу А. Психология бытия. Пер. с англ. О.О. Чистякова. – Рефл-бук: Ваклер, 1997. – 84 с.; Леонтьев А.А. Деятельностный ум

Pedagogical scientists K. Yoldoshev, S. Matchonov, M. Mirgosimova, R. A. Mavlyanova, D. Sharipova, O. Musurmonova, M. Kuronov, B. Abdulayeva, S. Nishonova, U. Mahkamov, E. Turdikulov, K. Husanboyeva, R. Safarova, B. Adizov, A. Choriev, Sh. Mardonov, D. Roziyeva, N. Egamberdiyeva, Sh. Shodmonova, Sh. Sharipov, O. It was cited in the scientific researches of pedagogic scientists such as Jamoldinova, V. Slastenin, I. Isayev, Ye. Shiyanov.

It should be noted that any lower level of inter-subject communication is established among certain didactic units within the studied subjects, and provides for the coordination of their study content and terms, in contrast to the educational subject organized on the basis of integrative communication or the subject being studied in an integrated manner requires the interpretation of events or processes in the form of a comprehensive system in terms of comprehensive communication and relationships. For this reason, the integration approach in the teaching methodology of pedagogues allows for the formation of a qualified professional person who thinks independently and shows creative activity.

In some pedagogical literature, integration is considered as the goal and means of education. Thus, the methodological analysis of different approaches to defining the meaning of the concept of "integration" shows that scientists and researchers interpret its application in different ways.

The process of integration significantly affects the development of the pedagogical idea, the development of scientific knowledge. The process of integration is the main form of interdisciplinary communication at the qualitatively new stage of education. It can be noted that the roots of the integration process lie in the long past of classical pedagogy and are closely related to the idea of interdisciplinary relations. The idea of interdisciplinary relations appears in the process of searching for ways to reflect the integrity of nature in the content of educational resources. The great didactic scientist John Amos Comenius states: "everything that communicates must be taught in the same communication." Later, many teachers turn to the idea of interdisciplinary relations by developing and generalizing it.

RESULTS

Continuing professional development of history teachers based on an integrated approach and increasing the level of competence through the special electronic platform "Continuous Professional Education", which covers the process of lifelong growth of the personal professional potential of history teachers in accordance with the needs of individuals and society. mechanism for improving the methodology is considered.

In this regard, the improvement of the methods of teaching history, the introduction of distance and other types of professional training, conducted together with the work process, as well as the traditional training of students in the system of continuous professional development, the interaction of educational institutions It is based on the integration of educational types based

(Деятельность. Знак. Личность). – М.: Смысл, 2001. – 392 с.; Давлетшин М.Г. Кобилият ва унинг диагностикаси. – Т.: Ўқитувчи, 1997. – 134 б.; Гозиев Э.Г. Психологические основы развитие самоуправления учебной деятельностью у школьников и студентов. Автореф. дис. ... док.псих.наук. – Т., 1991. – 38 с.; Каримова В. Психология. – Т.: Абдулла Қодирий номидаги халқ мероси нашриёти, 2002. – 204 б.; Суннатова Р.И. Индивидуально-типологические особенности мыслительной деятельности. Автореф. дис. ... док.псих. наук. – Т., 2001. – 41с.; Сафаев Н.С. Психологические особенности национального самосознания студенческой молодежи: Автореф. дис. ... доктора псих.наук. – Т., ТГПУ, 2006. – 38 с.; Нишонова З.Т. Мустақил ижодий фикрлашни шакллантиришининг психологик асослари: Псих.фан.док. ... дис. – Т., 2005.– 391 б.)

on equal cooperation and ensuring inter-disciplinary, integrated courses and inter-departmental coherence.

History teachers further develop their competence in the course of professional development courses, based on the unique methods of creating multimedia applications, working with tables, diagrams, maps, illustrations, in the integrated subject of teaching history based on the national curriculum.

As a result of the creative research of the teacher, the connection between the study of history and life together with the students on the basis of unique methods during the lessons leads to an increase in the level of knowledge of the students.

A number of reasons and factors affecting the competence of working with historical sources and literature and the choice of teaching methods were identified in the teaching of history. At the same time, the results of scientific research showed the importance of choosing the optimal methods for studying historical subjects in an integrated relationship:

- with the laws that apply in the educational process and the scientific-pedagogical principles arising from it;
- with the content and methods of the science of history in general and in particular (based on general and special pedagogy);
- with the goals and tasks of teaching;
- based on the content and character of the national curriculum and educational-methodical complexes based on it;
- on the basis of students' learning opportunities (characteristics of the class team, age, level and opportunities of psychological-physiological, educational-educational preparation);
- according to the capabilities of teachers (the level of theoretical and practical training, the use of certain methods and tools, the skills of choosing the most optimal options, interests and passions, communication culture, personal qualities, etc.).

Based on the requirements for the level of general knowledge and professional training of history teachers on the basis of continuous professional development course, abandoning the methods of oral teaching of history, teaching history on the basis of integrated education. focusing on teaching, teaching multimedia tools and independent work based on information technologies, organizing specialized and general professional subjects in training courses in harmony with each other is the most effective mechanism, in which the professional development of teachers enhances their creative abilities analyzes the coherence and consistency of the methods of teaching history through activation, improvement of personal skills and competences.

On the basis of the skills acquired by the teachers of historical sciences during the training, the students in the school education will be able to achieve efficiency with the variety of methods, methods and forms used in the educational process, as well as the study of historical realities, a conscious understanding of that period and learning from it will teach us not to repeat historical mistakes.

Integrative educational methods are classified into psychological, organizational, scientific, methodical, informational and other forms and are comprehensive, from the point of view of the object of our research. formation of elements of creative activity in the continuous professional development of teachers, development of ability, improvement of the system of conceptual foundations of historical thinking, information and communication technologies are fundamentally and methodically supported.

Designing teaching methods of history based on integrated education in continuous professional development, creating the necessary conditions for regular improvement of the professional skills and efficiency of pedagogues, continuous development of the system of professional development based on the principle of "lifelong learning" to improve their professional competences the following examples can be shown aimed at development:

Scientific and methodological materials: Providing history and social science e-textbooks, multimedia materials, web pages and subject-specific support materials for teachers.

Integrative approach: Tarix fanlarida fanlararo va fan mavzulari bo'yicha integratsion yondashuv.

Innovative teaching technologies: Highly interactive learning and teaching of subjects through the installation of virtual reality, interactive programs, computer applications and other technologies.

Information technologies: Development of materials on the basis of new technologies based on the national curriculum of teachers, critical and creative analysis.

✓ **There are three levels of education based on an integrated approach:**

intra-discipline—within separate disciplines (history, education. State and legal sciences);

interdisciplinary - synthesis of facts, concepts, principles of two or more disciplines;

interdisciplinary - a synthesis of the main and additional content of education.

On the basis of the methodological requirements for the level of general knowledge and professional training of history teachers on the basis of the continuous professional methodology improvement course, on the basis of the integrative approach, history teachers are trained in information technologies and independent skills based on various educational methods. great importance is attached to increase.

Through this, the improvement of innovative methods and technologies for the development of students' thinking outlook is becoming more important.

CONCLUSION

The goal of interaction-based education is to develop creative skills and competencies, to form creative professional methods. Consolidation of new knowledge obtained in the lecture, improvement of certain professional skills and qualifications, and development of continuous professional methods based on an integrated approach to solve the following tasks: analysis of a specific situation.

To provide the basis for the continuous development of professional and pedagogical methods of history teachers, the regular updating of their professional knowledge, qualifications and skills on advanced pedagogical and information technologies, as well as interactive methods of teaching. consists of riding.

Based on the above, it can be said that in improving the methodology of teaching history, it is possible to achieve educational efficiency by ensuring coherence on the basis of integrated education based on the general laws and principles of pedagogy.

In preparing teachers to implement integrated education in the course of the lesson, it is necessary to give a clear direction to the methods of science and direct them to use their capabilities effectively. In particular, on the basis of the national curriculum, the main criteria for choosing the appropriate methodological methods for improving the effectiveness of the lesson by connecting the knowledge, skills, skills and competences of the students in the subject of history on the basis of integration education will be developed.

In this, the minimum requirements that must be mastered by students according to the national curriculum are determined for each subject, and the place of inter-course connections is determined.

In conclusion, it can be said that by improving the continuous professional methodology of history teachers on the basis of an integrated approach, the organization of a continuous professional development system based on the national curriculum will create the necessary conditions for the continuous growth of their professional skills and qualifications. aimed at training in accordance with modern requirements and regularly updating its methods.

Based on the integrative approach, improving the skills of history teachers, as well as their professional development and manifestation of their talent based on the principle of "Life-long learning", and the ways to achieve creative achievements in their professional activities are directed to a scientific methodical analysis.

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